

Writing a Script for a Short Video Promotion of Dapoer Cinta as a Culinary Destination in Palembang

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ABSTRACT: The purpose of this study was to find out how to write a script for a short video of Dapoer Cinta to promote one of the culinary destinations in Palembang. Using a Research and Development (R&D) method adapted from Plomp (1997), with a qualitative descriptive design, the steps in designing the script were (1) preliminary investigation; (2) designing; (3) realization/development; (4) testing, evaluation, and revision; and (5) implementation. The data collection techniques were literature studies, observations, and interviews. Then, the data analysis was carried out through a qualitative descriptive method. There were 3 experts selected purposively to participate in revising the script: an Indonesian language expert, writing style expert, and an English expert. The data revealed that to produce a good promotional short video script, each expert suggested the following revisions. The Indonesian language expert recommended to revise the selection of words that were appropriate to PUEBI. Then writing style expert suggested to remove inappropriate sentences, and to change some sentences to be more efficient. Next, the English language expert suggested to revise grammatical errors, sentence structure, inappropriate use of transition signals, and inappropriate sentence changes. Finally, after the final text was approved and there were no further revisions, the script could be used as a short video script to promote Dapoer Cinta as a culinary destination in Palembang.

Keywords: *culinary tourism, promotion, short video*

INTRODUCTION

Culinary tourism has become an increasingly important aspect of the tourism industry, as many travelers are now seeking authentic culinary experiences when they visit a new city or country. This is because traditional food and drink provide a unique insight into the local culture and way of life of a place which is interesting for the visitors of that place. Traditional culinary uniqueness is a primary reason why people visit a particular destination, making it a key factor in attracting visitors and boosting tourism revenue. Abhiyoga & Febreani (2021) stated that the culinary industry in Indonesia has great potential to be developed into a tourism destination for both international and local tourists, due to the diversity of unique foods and drinks in every region.

Palembang, with its lush traditional culinary, is a potential destination for culinary tourism. With its abundance of culinary establishments, visitors can easily find traditional Palembang foods. Tekwan, Model, Laksan, Pindang, Mie Celor, Burgo, Celimpungan, and Pempek are among the Palembang traditional foods, each offering a unique taste. In Palembang, one of the restaurants that sell traditional Palembang food is Dapoer Cinta. Not only selling traditional Palembang food nowadays but also traditional food of the past, commonly known as Bingen culinary. Dapoer Cinta restaurant is a restaurant that sells traditional foods such as Pempek, Tekwan, Burgo, Maksuba, Pindang Patin, etc. also sells some old traditional foods or Bingen culinary like Gulo Palu, Kumbu Kacang, Dadar Jiwo, Jando Beraes, and so on. This restaurant has some beautiful spots and an Instagram-able spot with the Musi River as a view. Moreover, there is a boat on the bank Musi River for a special eating place.

Unfortunately, Dapoer Cinta remains unknown due to a lack of information and promotion about its location. This factor causes the restaurant to be unnoticed and unknown by Palembang's visitors. Therefore, this restaurant must utilize promotional media to communicate its existence effectively and attract more customers. Then, to make the restaurant more recognizable and known by many people, several media channels can be used to disseminate information about this restaurant.

Several media channels are available to promote Dapoer Cinta restaurant such as booklets, posters, blogs, magazines, banners, videos, and so on. However, a short video has become more preferred by many people nowadays as it provides a visual and auditory experience while easily conveying information. Therefore, a short video in the promotional strategy can enhance the visibility and attractiveness of the location.

A short video can be an effective promotional tool. A short video is more likely to

capture people's attention and keep them engaged compared to long-form content. This is especially true for mobile users, who tend to consume content in short bursts. Additionally, short video is easier to consume because they require less time and effort compared to longer videos or other types of content. Moreover, Sheldon (2023) argues that short video is more shareable, cost-effective, and can convey a message quickly and efficiently. It encourages businesses to use short-form videos to promote their products or services and suggests that this type of content will continue to gain importance in the future.

Having Dapoer Cinta as the object of this article, the writer conducted an article for writing a script for a short video promotion of Dapoer Cinta as a Culinary Destination in Palembang.

METHOD

The writer used Research and Development (R&D) method. The method is designed to improve the success rate of new product development projects (Cooper & Schindler, 2011). Previously, Borg & Gall (1983) argued the R&D method as a cyclical process that entails methodically and under controlled conditions designing and evaluating a product or procedure. The R&D method has ten steps: (1) research and information collection, (2) planning, (3) developing a preliminary form of product, (4) preliminary field testing, (5) revising the main product, (6) main field testing, (7) revising operational field testing, (8) operational field testing, (9) revising final product, (10) disseminating and implementing.

Later in 1997, Plomp also argued another R&D Method which was simpler because it only has 5 steps, shorter than Borg & Gall's model with 10 steps. The model was more adaptable to the context of this project because each stage could be modified to account

for the writer's setting and personal traits, especially due to the limitation of time and budget (Gustiani, 2019). The steps in Plomp's models are preliminary investigation, designing, realization/construction, testing, evaluation, revision, and implementation as shown in Figure 1.

Source: Plomp (1997)

Description:

Figure 1. The Stages of R&D Method

The subject of this research were the people who had participated and offered their knowledge and information in the project's evaluation, revision, and realization until the final result. The three experts were the Indonesian language teacher at Senior Highschool Number 19 Palembang as an expert in Indonesian grammar, Copywriter as a writing style expert, and the English language teacher at State Polyte as an English grammar expert. First, the writer presented the product to the Indonesian language teacher, Mrs. Rita Karlina Silaen, M. Pd. She made some changes to the Indonesian script that the writer had drafted. Mrs. Herninda Biocella as a Copywriter, reviewed the writing style of English

script. Finally, Mrs. Fitri Yanti, M. Pd as an English language expert gave comments on the script's grammar. Purposive sampling was used by the writer to select participants for this research. Creswell (2007) stated that purposive sampling is a strategy for selecting samples based on specific aims and reasons. Purposive sampling entailed the researcher to use their skills to pick a sample that was most relevant to the research objectives

FINDINGS

Preliminary Investigation

A preliminary investigation is a study of concepts or theories for the product that was developed in this research. For the first step, the writer studied the concept of theories related to the product, such as the definition of script, the language style of scriptwriting, and culinary tourism and also the writer read the articles about the short video and *Dapoer Cinta* to find the ideas of how to write a good short video script.

Literature Study

A literature study is a study of concepts or theories related to the product that was developed in this research. For the first step, the writer studied the concept of theories related to the product, such as the definition of writing, and the definition of a short video also the writer read the journals, and articles about scriptwriting included in a script.

Field Survey

Besides doing a literature study, the writer conducted field survey in *Dapoer Cinta* through observations on the situation of the restaurant, such as the products, services, and facilities. Based on the observation, the writer found that *Dapoer Cinta* needed improvements, such as providing Wi-Fi and a parking area that would attract tourists or local people who would want to come to *Dapoer Cinta*.

Arranging Model Draft

The writer started to make the script based on the elements of scriptwriting by Jakacaping (2018). There are three elements, namely hook, opening, body, and closing. The writer typed the text in Microsoft Word 2019. The texts were written in two versions: English and Indonesian.

Model Development

The second stage was Model Development which consisted of designing, realization/construction, and (testing, revising, and evaluation).

Designing

After getting information from the literature study, obtaining the data from the field survey, and arranging the model draft based on Jakacaping (2018), the writer organized it and made the materials of the script that consisted of hook, opening, body, and closing. The table is presented below.

Table 1. *Script Text Structure and Materials*

Parts	Materials
Hook	The benefits of coming to <i>Dapoer Cinta</i>
Opening	The highlights of <i>Dapoer Cinta</i>
Body	The facilities, menu and price, and opening hour of <i>Dapoer Cinta</i>
Closing	The location and transportation at <i>Dapoer Cinta</i> , and Call to Action (CTA)

Realization/Construction

In realization/construction, the writer started to make a first draft based on the structure and material. The first draft was written in Indonesian and translated into English.

Table 2. First Draft of English Script

Culinary Sensation by the Musi River Palembang

Hook

For those of you who want to experience the cheap, delicious, and many traditional food specialties of Palembang city with an atmosphere on the banks of the Musi river, Then, you should definitely visit *Dapoer Cinta!*

Opening

The view of the Musi riverbank and the architecture of Palembang *Bingen* are the highlights of *Dapoer Cinta* itself. Plus, it serves traditional *Bingen* snacks that are so cheap that you don't have to worry about your wallet.

Body

Dapoer Cinta takes a unique view of the Musi river. Because everyday there are various types of ships sailing. Starting from small boats, to large ones. For your Information, Dapoer Cinta is in the middle between the journey from Benteng Kuto Besak to Kemaro island. Therefore, Dapoer Cinta can be the best option as a checkpoint for visitors who want to relax and rest before continuing their journey. Even Dapoer Cinta also provides 4 units of boats with officers that you can use for water tours starting from the Dapoer Cinta pier itself.

As someone who has never visited the place, you must be curious, what are the facilities available there. Dapoer Cinta uses 100% unglan wood, which is commonly used for South Sumatra's traditional Limas houses. The building includes 6 Gazebos with colorful roofs. Not only that, there is 1 large gazebo for those of you who want to relax with friends and family. In this large gazebo, there is live music which is usually held on Thursday, Friday and Saturday.

Uniquely, , there is also a place with 3 kajang boats that you can use to dine while feeling the cool breeze and beautiful scenery. In addition, they also provide power outlets with electricity in each gazebo. So, your laptop and handphone will not run out of battery in this place.

Then, this café provides everything from light meals to heavy foods. For the heavy food itself, there are various kinds of pindang such as chicken, fish, bone, and meat pindang. And there is also Palembang specialty rice, namely Nasi Minyak Arab and Nasi Kebulli. For the price itself is relatively inexpensive and not cheap at 35,000 Rupiah which can

already choose for side dishes, soup, chili sauce, and eggs. For snacks, Dapoer Cinta also provides a variety of bingen cakes. Bingen cakes means traditional cakes of Palembang city that are very rarely found. Bingen cakes include kue pare, dadar jiwo, kue gelenak, kue lumpang, Jando berais and many more. And there is no need to ask again about the special food that is very famous in South Sumatra precisely in the city of Palembang namely pempek, in this café provides various types of pempek such as pempek kapal selam, pempek lenjer, pempek adaan, and so on. Even for traditional food typical of Palembang city is priced at a very affordable price ranging from 2000 to 20000 Rupiah.

Apart from snacks, Dapoer Cinta also serves soupy foods, such as celimpungan, laksan, lakso, burgo, martabak kari, tekwan, model ikan, rujak mie, mi klenger, bubur sumsum, jongkong, and mi celor. All the food is priced at affordable prices, ranging from 12,000 to 20,000 rupiah.

Closing

To get to this location, you can go directly west from the Musi IV Bridge. For cars, you can park at Mosque “Al-Hadad”. There is an arrow showing the direction to *Dapoer Cinta*. However, for motorcycles, you can park directly in front of *Dapoer Cinta*. On the way to *Dapoer Cinta* from *Kampung Kuliner Bingen Palembang*, you will be presented with a beautiful view of *Bari* houses. In addition, for those of you who want to feel the maritime atmosphere, you can use public transportation in the form of a *Kajang* boat from *Benteng Kuto Besak*.

Curious? Go straight to *Dapoer Cinta*!

Testing, Revising, and Evaluation

In testing, the writer gave the first draft to the experts. Firstly, the writer gave the Indonesian script to Mrs. Rita Kartika Silaen, M. Pd. as an Indonesian grammar expert. She said that the script was good. However, she gave some suggestions in closing that needed to add specific information. After getting the revision of the Indonesian script, the writer translated the revision of the Indonesian script into English script. Next, the writer gave the English script to Mrs. Herninda Biocella as a writing style expert. She gave the comment that the script needs to add more transition signals and changed some words to more variety. Some of the examples of the revisions were written in the table below. For the English grammar, the writer gave the English script to Mrs. Fitri Yanti, M.Pd. She corrected some

grammatical errors in the script. Moreover, she said that making numbers in a sentence had to be done consistently.

Implementation

The final product was supposed to be implemented in a video. However, the video was not made due to the limitation of the cost, time, and not being in the department's scope. Therefore, the final product was only the script of the video. The following were the final versions of the English version and the Bahasa Indonesia version. The final product had 2 versions, such as the Indonesian script and the English script. The final product was written in the Table 4.

Table 4. Final Product of English Script

Culinary Sensation by the Musi River Palembang

For those of you who want to experience traditional food typical of the city of Palembang that is cheap, delicious, and presented with a view of the banks of the *Musi* River. Then, you definitely should visit *Dapoer Cinta*!

The view of the Musi riverbank and the architecture of Palembang *Bingen* are the highlights of *Dapoer Cinta*. Furthermore, you will be served traditional *Bingen* snacks at affordable prices and of course delicious. So, you don't have to worry about your wallet anymore.

Dapoer Cinta takes a unique view of the *Musi* river. Because every day there are various types of ships sailing. Starting from small boats, to large ones. For your information, *Dapoer Cinta* is in the middle between the journey from *Benteng Kuto Besak* to *Kemaro* island. Therefore, *Dapoer Cinta* can be the best option as a checkpoint for visitors who want to relax and rest before continuing their journey. Even *Dapoer Cinta* also provides 4 units of boats with officers that you can use for water tours starting from the *Dapoer Cinta* pier itself.

As someone who has never visited the place, you must be curious, what are the facilities available there. *Dapoer Cinta* uses 100% *unglen* wood, which is commonly used for South Sumatra's traditional *Limas* houses. The building includes six Gazebos with colorful roofs. Not only that, there is one large gazebo for those of you who want to relax with friends and family. In this large gazebo, there is live music which is usually held on Thursday, Friday and Saturday.

Uniquely, there is also a place with 3 *kajang* boats that you can use to dine while feeling the cool breeze and beautiful scenery. In addition, they also provide power outlets with electricity in each gazebo. So, your laptop and cellphone won't run out of battery in this place.

Then, this café provides everything from light meals to heavy foods. For the heavy food itself, there are various kinds of *pindang* such as chicken, fish, bone, and meat *pindang*. And there is also Palembang specialty rice, namely *Nasi Minyak Arab* and *Nasi Kebulli*. For the price itself is relatively inexpensive and not cheap at 35,000 Rupiah which can already choose for side dishes, soup, chili sauce, and eggs. For snacks, *Dapoer Cinta* also provides a variety of *bingen* cakes. *Bingen* cakes means traditional cakes of Palembang city that are very rarely found. *Bingen* cakes include *kue pare*, *dadar jiwo*, *kue gelenak*, *kue lumpang*, *Jando berais* and many more. And there is no need to ask again about the special food that is very famous in South Sumatra precisely in the city of Palembang namely *pempek*, in this café provides various types of *pempek* such as *pempek kapal selam*, *pempek lenjer*, *pempek adaan*, and so on. The snacks and *pempek* are sold at prices ranging from 2000 to 5000 rupiah.

Apart from snacks, *Dapoer Cinta* also serves soupy foods, such as *celimpungan*, *laksan*, *lakso*, *burgo*, *martabak kari*, *tekwan*, *model ikan*, *rujak mie*, *mi klenger*, *bubur sumsum*, *jongkong*, and *mi celor*. Moreover, all traditional foods unique to Palembang city are only priced at very affordable prices ranging from Rp. 2.000 to Rp. 20.000.

In addition, for its own operating hours, from Monday to Thursday, it is open from 11 am to 9 pm. Then, from Friday to Sunday, *Dapoer Cinta* will open from 7 am to 9 pm.

To get to this location, you can go directly west from the Musi IV Bridge, Then, about 400 m you will see an alley with the words “Kampung Kuliner Bingen Palembang”. Then, just follow the road. For those of you who bring a car, you can park at the Mosque “Al- Hadad”. However, for motorcycles, you can park directly in front of *Dapoer Cinta*. There is an arrow showing the direction to *Dapoer Cinta*. You only need to walk about 100 m to get there. On the way to *Dapoer Cinta* from Kampung Kuliner Bingen Palembang, you will be presented with a beautiful view of Bari houses. In addition, for those of you who want to feel the maritime atmosphere, you can use public transportation in the form of a *Kajang* boat from Benteng Kuto Besak.

Curious? Go straight to *Dapoer Cinta*!

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

The writer had shown the first draft of the Script to the experts. The script was about Writing a Script for a Short Video Promotion of *Dapoer Cinta* as a Culinary Destination in Palembang, and it was revised based on the suggestion from the experts in testing, revision, and evaluation. Therefore, this

section discussed about the mistakes in Indonesian grammar, writing style, and English grammar.

In testing, the writer asked Mrs. Rita Karmila Silaen to check the Indonesian grammar based on the Pedoman Umum Ejaan Bahasa Indonesia (Tim Pengembang Pedoman Bahasa Indonesia, 2016). She said that the use of letters such as the alphabet, capital letters, italics was correct. Then, the writing of words such as basic words, compound words, compound words, and pronouns was also good. However, she commented on the closing sentence that informed about the location of Dapoer Cinta which was still unclear. Therefore, she suggested that more detailed information be given regarding the location of Dapoer Cinta.

Besides the Indonesian grammar, the writing style of the Script was also revised. In this stage, the expert was Mrs. Herninda Biocella for writing style of the script. She revised the writing style of the script, and she said that the script was persuasive. This was related to the theory given by Agustrijanto (2001) that persuasive convincing the audience to use the introduced or given product right away. In the first draft, the sentence was *“For those of you who want to experience traditional food typical of the city of Palembang that is cheap, delicious, and presented with a view of the banks of the Musi River. Then, you definitely should visit Dapoer Cinta!”* Moreover, Mrs. Herninda Biocella said that the elements in the script were appropriate with the theory given by Jakacaping (2018) that there are four crucial components to consider when creating a successful script starting from hook, opening, body, and closing. Therefore, she said what was meant in each point of the theory was in accordance with the first draft. Furthermore, Mrs. Herninda Biocella discussed about the distinction. In script writing, connecting words or sentences such as where are frequently used so that the listener or reader understands the desired storyline. It also needs an awareness of the topic's emphasis, such as not deviating from the main topic. In conclusion, she suggested to inserts a connecting sentence in each paragraph to make the paragraphs more structured.

Likewise, Geysner (2023) mentioned that the nature of the short video platforms is that users scroll up to quickly go from video to video. This means it is extremely easy for viewers to scroll past your

video if it does not immediately draw them in. To combat this, start with a hook. Similarly, Jakacaping (2018) mentioned that the script should start with a hook to keep the viewers engaged. Furthermore, Mrs. Herninda Biocella commented that the hook contained in the script used was a selective headline which was one of the best choices as a hook of a script to attract the attention of the audience.

Lastly, the writer gave the English Script to Mrs. Fitri Yanti. She corrected the grammatical errors and suggested to change Indonesian terms into italic. This related to (Hirai et al., 2010) who states that grammar is a way to organize the sentence and create a good language. In the first draft, the sentence was “*you should definitely visit Dapoer Cinta!*”. It was added become “*you definitely should visit Dapoer Cinta!*”. Therefore, Mrs. Fitri Yanti suggested that putting the adverb at the beginning after the subject was more efficient which made the grammar more organized and good language.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

From the explanation in the previous chapters, the writer concluded to use the R&D Method by Plomp (1997) which had 5 steps, such as preliminary investigation, designing, realization/construction, testing, evaluation, revision, and implementation. In preliminary investigation, the writer studied the concept of theories and read the articles related to the product. Then, There were three experts involved in the testing. They were Mrs. Rita Karlina Silaen, M. Pd., an Indonesian language Teacher at Senior Highschool Number 19 Palembang. Mrs. Herninda Biocella as a writing style expert. Mrs. Fitri Yanti, M. Pd., an English language Teacher at Senior Highschool Number 19 Palembang. First, In Indonesian language, the expert gave some suggestions in the closing which required the addition of specific information. Then, In writing style, the expert provided comments that the script needed to have more transition signals and to change some words for better variation. Last, the English grammar of the script was checked by the expert of English grammar. After the revision and there was no other revision, the final

product was done. However, the video was not produced due to the limitation of the cost, time, and study scope.

REFERENCES

- Abhiyoga, N., & Febreani, Y. K. (2021). Strategi gastrodiplomasi tempe oleh Diaspora Indonesia di Amerika Serikat. *Padjadjaran Journal of International Relations*, 3(2), 186–198. Retrieved on May 15, 2023 from <https://doi.org/10.24198/padmir.v3i2.31172.31172>
- Agustrijanto. (2001). *Copywriting: Seni mengasah kreativitas dan memahami bahasa iklan*. Bandung: Remaja Rosdakarya.
- Borg, W. R., & GALL, M.. (1983). *Educational research; An introduction*. New York: Longman.
- Cooper, D. R., & Schindler, P. (2011). *Business Research Methods (11th ed.)*. Boston: McGraw-Hill Education.
- Creswell, J. W. (2012). *Educational research: Planning, conducting, and evaluating quantitative and qualitative research (4th ed.)*. Boston: MA Pearson.
- Geyser, W. (2023). The ultimate guide to short-form video content. *Influencer Marketing Hub*. Retrieved on April 10, 2023 from <https://influencermarketinghub.com/short-form-video-content/>
- Gustiani, S. (2019). Research and Development (R&D) method as a model design in educational research and its alternatives. *Holistic Journal*, 11(2). Retrieved on April 27, 2023 from [file:///C:/Users/user/Downloads/1849-Article Text-2835-1-10-20200103 \(4\).pdf](file:///C:/Users/user/Downloads/1849-Article Text-2835-1-10-20200103 (4).pdf)
- Hirai, D. L. C., Borrego, I., Garza, E., & Kloock, C. (2010). Academic language/literacy strategies for adolescents. In *Academic Language/Literacy Strategies for Adolescents*. London: Routledge. Retrieved on May 20, 2023 from <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203859575>
- Jakacaping, D. (2018). Cara membuat script video [video]. Youtube: <https://youtu.be/BN->

aTwoGDSE

Plomp, T. (1997). Development research on/in educational development.

Netherlands: Twente University.

Tim Pengembang Pedoman Bahasa Indonesia. (2016). Pedoman umum ejaan Bahasa Indonesia.

Jakarta Timur: Badan Pengembangan dan Pembinaan Bahasa Kementerian Pendidikan dan Kebudayaan.